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**Entrepreneurial Sustainability in the Context of Spirituality among Micro Restaurants
Business Owners**

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on entrepreneur's sustainability under the context of spirituality of micro restaurants business owners. As such, assumptions were made; Spirituality is defined by the entrepreneurs in the micro scale restaurant business in the context of vision, character and humanity. Second spirituality was the guidepost for the opportunities, threats and challenges that the entrepreneurs faced in the conduct of their business. Third is the spirituality sustain the motivation of the entrepreneurs in the conduct of their business. This research utilized a phenomenological method to gain an understanding of underlying reasons, opinions, and motivations. The conclusion was made that; Spirituality is a connection to God regardless of religious affiliation, constant communication through prayers that guides them in doing business. Under the context of spirituality, proponent's vision is to help and uplift the stakeholders, and to their employees by giving them the basic needs and education as means of providing them with better future when they leave the business. Spirituality is framed into vision, giving the best possible future for the employee's family, the character and integrity. Under the context of spirituality, entrepreneurs were able to overcome the threats and challenges due to values it carries and it projects to its employees. Focusing on good customer's services, quality of product, transparency with regard to the current issues in prices increase, earning trust that resulted into customer loyalty. In sustaining the motivation of the entrepreneurs, it is concluded that spirituality gives an entrepreneur an extra energy believing that if they pray and dedicate everything God, it strengthens their soul and rejuvenate their weary body.

INTRODUCTION

Being in the category of micro business is not as simple as meeting the minimum or little capital and enjoy smaller and manageable subordinates but the real deal is how businessmen were able to sustain the business in dealing with competitors, how they were able to handle the struggle and get a chunk of pie of the market in their respective areas. Researches look into the personality an entrepreneur's as factor in the sustainability of the business.

According to Nandan (2012), personality is the composite character denoting the totality of the individual such as attitudes, habits, emotional tendencies and behavioural patterns. But does all of it answers the questions in relation to the entrepreneur's motivation in sustaining the business as factor to success alone? In this research, the proponent looked into a different perspective of success as sustaining and surviving the harsh competition of industry in the micro restaurant level under the context of spirituality. The personality of the entrepreneurs is a factor to consider but does spirituality had given entrepreneurs an extra mile in sustaining the business and moving to the next level? Is spirituality another avenue to look at? The owner, the personnel and staff of the business compose the team that sustain the industry. It is on this light that the researcher shall explore the sustaining entrepreneurial motivations of selected successful micro restaurant business in the context of spirituality. Emami and Nazari (2012) confirmed that religiously committed entrepreneurs exhibited a

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less tolerant attitude than others in the matter. In the research conducted by Petchsawanga, P. and Duchon, D. (2012), shows that people who regularly practice meditation have higher workplace spirituality scores than people who do not regularly practice meditation. From this concept, the proponent will look into the spirituality as subject that is to be tested wherein spirituality is a factor why business owners were able to sustain the challenges in business. A lot of business fails despite having skills, resources and financial capability and at the same time are those aforementioned factors because they fail to include spirituality to be successful. Furthermore, M-Said Oikil (2013) said that spiritual leadership, common to all religious entrepreneurs, often combines personal and others' interest, this is to say that people do not live in a vacuum, and at extreme situations, spirituality could help them in life, in general and in business, in particular, to stay away from wrong doings and consequently sins. Why is the researcher interested on micro restaurant entrepreneurs? These micro-restaurant businesses have already taken their niche in the market catering to a greater number of people whether in urban or rural areas. With ample years of existence, they have already developed their organizational culture with their corresponding vision and values. Micro restaurants are still in the process of finding their niche in the business world and struggling to make a difference for sustainability. Most of businesses prosper because of good marketing, brand, position and etc. continuous improvement and development of the organization and its products. The proponent is more curious with regard to the entrepreneur's motivations sustainability in the context of spirituality; Visions that does not only focused on profit and expansion but also for the benefit of its stakeholders, its actions and ways of doing business inspires and motivate aspirants and undoubted integrity (Levine, 2016).

This study will be a significant endeavour since it will deal with the elements known before as only applicable to religion and philosophy but has presently been used in the business context. Specifically, this study will benefit the following: **Restaurant Entrepreneurs.** For them to go beyond the issue of profit and expansion, to have that desire to share business to humanity. The stories of success that may have been moulded by opportunities, threats and challenges but have been strengthened by spirituality and can serve as inspiration. As a restaurant owner, it is important to understand the components that go into customers' value judgments, in order to maximize the perceived value that they provide, thus increasing customer satisfaction. **Future Restaurant Entrepreneurs.** Practically oriented and can work as entrepreneurs or in different organizations and companies as experts and managers, they are able to employ analytical skills in decision-making and will have the competence in establishing and operating their own enterprises.

Assumptions:

1. Spirituality is defined by the entrepreneurs in the micro scale restaurant business in the context of vision, character and humanity.
2. Spirituality was the guidepost for the opportunities, threats and challenges that the entrepreneurs faced in the conduct of their business.
3. Spirituality sustain the motivation of the entrepreneurs in the conduct of their business.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the qualitative research. Qualitative data collection methods vary using unstructured or semi-structured techniques. Some common methods include focus groups discussions, individual interviews, and participation/observations. The sample size is typically small, and respondents are selected to fulfil a given quota. (Wyse, 2011). This study utilized phenomenological method to gain an understanding of underlying reasons, opinions, and motivations. It provided insights into the problem or helped to develop ideas or hypotheses for potential quantitative research. It also uncovered trends in thought and opinions, and dived deeper into the problem (Wyse, 2011). This research described the lived experiences of the micro-restaurant entrepreneurs as they find themselves doing their business guided by spirituality.

Locale of the Study and Key Informants

This study was conducted in Metro Manila and purposively chose eight micro restaurant entrepreneurs who are willingly agreed to be the key informants of the study. Classification of the restaurants was based on the Senate of the Philippine Government classification of Medium Scale Enterprises of 2012 as those with the capital from less than 3 million pesos in capital assets and employees not exceeding nine (9).

Research Instruments

This study used an unstructured interview guide prepared by the researcher based from the varied literature where assumptions were culled. Paper and pen served as the primary tools aided by tape recorder and video recording upon approval of the respondents. The researcher opted not to include the video recording as one of the appendices since some of the key informants wanted to remain anonymous. The interview was supported by participant observation to intensify the value of the concepts and findings.

Impediments of the Research

Out of forty-nine (49) target respondents around metro manila, only eight (8) are willing to cooperate and participated in the research. The forty-one respondent who did not participate gave their reason, the following are their reasons for not participating; they are not good in English, too shy to be interviewed, lack of confidence to answer the questions provided, and too busy to spare an hour for the interview.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Key Informants

The key informants of the study were eight (8) micro and small restaurant entrepreneurs whose businesses are found within the Metro Manila Area. Three of the entrepreneurs preferred to be anonymous while the three (3) find it casual to be identified.

The longest year of business operation is 30 years followed by 25 years. The six having an average of 17 years of business existence.

As to the number of employees, one restaurant has nine employees while the rest have an average of eight employees.

Spirituality in Business

A common meaning of spirituality is to involve oneself in activities that can renew, lift up, comfort, heal and inspire both themselves and those with whom they interact with. Spirituality is equated with religion but this is regardless of what religious denomination one belongs to. Lifting up refers to going beyond the worldly things and going closer to a higher purpose. Often enough, spirituality is associated with faith, beliefs and values in life.

For a businessman, spirituality means the values and traits, how he should act and conduct his business not only toward the customers but also with peers and his employees.

Spirituality is direct relationship with God, a relationship that means communication to God through prayers, the means by which one can freely tell God his messages and thoughts. It has direct relationship with faith. Spirituality is something that originates from inside the individual. It is the existences of an inner consciousness and the feeling of connectedness to others and with one's work. Such faith is a manifestation of faith and gratefulness done in going to church amidst business and never forget to pray and give thanks to Him.

Spirituality means two things: first, a connection to something greater than themselves and second, a

sense of meaning and purpose that guides their lives.

Entrepreneurial Spirituality through Vision and Inspiration

In western society, spirituality is rather a way of life to work on self-realization, connectedness to others, and doing good to society rather than religious beliefs [beliefs] and practices (Nandran, 2009). This philosophy is the same practice in the Asian context especially among Filipinos whose life is always guided by the attitude of "bahala na". In the positive context, this is a vision that relates to where the words originated, "Bathala na" indicating a strong belief with the guidance of the Omnipotent in the course of doing something for the future.

" Yes, every time you are to do something, like when you are requesting a favour, you need to pray because that will serve as your guide and source of strength and your belief goes into achieving your vision for yourself. But of course, prayers are not enough, it would require actions too and by playing your role accordingly. That's how one will achieve his vision."

Any entrepreneur's vision for his endeavour is profitability, the sustenance of business until it reaches its success.

" I realize little by little that vision is needed in doing our daily activities or transactions for our business. This will also include vision on what are you supposed to do, what kind of market you will be interacting with and what kind of products you will be selling. Being in a restaurant business, our vision to offer products of quality consistently."

The spiritual practice of vision encompasses the discovery of fresh insights about the way things are and the cultivation of different outlooks on what can be. It is how you find your own wisdom and align yourself with Spirit.

There are two major conflicts that arise with this definition and business practices. The first conflict comes with the expectation of going beyond "worldly things" while for-profit businesses are supposed to be all about amassing wealth. The second conflict comes in with the implication of lifting up others which goes against the selfish and aggressive personality traits typically associated with successful corporate executives.

When business organizations and entrepreneurs become successful and prosperous, they start looking for a purpose beyond money and power. Maslow's hierarchy of needs offers explanation for this change. Once the more basic survival, safety, self-esteem needs are fulfilled, there is a need for self-actualization through a higher purpose. As society achieves more prosperity, individuals and hence corporations become more free to pay attention to social work and raising the standards of treatment of employees. (Desal, 2005). The same thing is true for the restaurant entrepreneurs, having started a vision for the comfort of their own family and later extending such to their employees and even their families.

" I considered my family as my top priority. I don't want my kids to experience the same difficulties I went through before when I was in highschool up to college, I need to work during the day and study at night. I do not want them to undergo the same. That is why I hold on closely and work harder for them. I cling on to God's mercy, and right now, my youngest is already graduating."

" I also send some of my workers to school. I check on them from time-to-time. Some of them are also sending someone to school. At times, they come to us for help to support whom they are sending to school for tuition fees."

" For me, my vision is to help my family and also the families of my workers. So they will all graduate. I send them all to school. This, I believe can give them good future."

The entrepreneur should also have the ability to imprint his vision to drive not only his, but also his

team's energy and motivation, instilling in them the same enthusiasm, drive and perseverance that brings projects and dreams to fruition. Because a vision that is unshared and does not echo into other people is not a vision. A vision needs to be believed, nurtured and followed in order to become the lighthouse that guides the endeavour.

Mark Zuckerberg, the founder and CEO of Facebook, who continues to personally welcome all new employees, despite his company's staff count now reaching the around 10,000-person mark. The latter approach is what H.H. Sheikh Mohammed Bin Rashid Al Maktoum, Vice President of the UAE and Ruler of Dubai, has used, who, after setting a ambitious and disruptive vision for his country, has been able to attract the best talents, nurture them, and ultimately empower them to implement this vision in their own doains of expertise (dela Torre, 2016).

“ And also, those workers who expressed their intentions of working overseas, we do not necessarily stop them because we do not have any control as to how they want their future will be, as long as they will be fine, why can't we not allow them to go. Right now, we are having new employees because some of them worked overseas. I help them, some of them are coming Palawan province, in Coron specifically. For those who wanted to continue their studies, I support them. That is what I am emphasizing to them, that the business is not only for us, the business is also existing to help others as well. I believe if you cannot help people, the business will not run well. If we are the only ones running it (with my wife), it is nothing, therefore, we have to help each other.”

The vision of entrepreneurs anchored on spirituality goes beyond oneself and earning a profit. It is not just the betterment of his own family but providing the chances of a better quality of life to the families of his employees through hard but decent work. Most of the entrepreneurs believe that giving the family members the chance for education is already a good vision. A good vision is also the chance to allow and support the employees to spread their wings and provide them opportunities to grow.

Believing in the cause, matters a lot. If people believe in themselves and the team members, no problem is too large, they do not easily get discouraged or overwhelmed when envisioning what could be. They are more open to new ideas. The team is more likely to innovate.

Restaurant employees need to understand and share the vision of the owner. The vision will motivate and inspire them for it will mean giving them a reason to believe and improve their morale.

Spirituality in Business is the Integration of Corporate Social Responsibility

If spirituality means values and traits, attitudes that pertain to the goodness of a person towards other people and the community at large; therefore, it is highly interconnected with the practice of corporate social responsibility especially among the fast growing industry of restaurant. The restaurant industry is one of the fastest emerging sectors in the world. CSR, also called Corporate Social Responsibility, is a cumulative of ethics and duties which engage any business in looking at their impact on society and assessing their responsibilities towards the employees, customers, and both the society and the stockholders. In restaurants, the CSR depends on the legal and functional duties which they have to perform to benefit the society.

The restaurant industry gives employment to unskilled, semi skilled and skilled people on different designation. It allows building and enhancing the personal skills by providing training to the workers. In this way, they can create a prefect and friendly atmosphere and serve the community. In the restaurant industry, CSR is a new ideat; there are a lot of multinational food chains which are involved in the activities related to CSR. There are many financial as well as societal benefits to be found from from developing a CSR policy within a restaurant. The restaurant industry has taken various voluntary actions to involve in the development of society and the owners. This initiative represents the devotion of restaurants staff and owner towards the sustainable growth

Many of them today believe that there is more to life and business than profits alone. In today's business world, values and ethics are given due attention. Today business buzz within CSR is the

“triple bottom line”(people, planet, profit) by Fry& Nisiewicz (2013). Economics has been evolved around employees and the environment; therefore, giving due attention to spiritual values into the workplace build great sense of spirit in the work environment. Spiritually-aware managers and businesses consider themselves servants of employees, customers, and the community.

“I don’t treat myself as a boss I’m just like them, I’m just like them, . As you see in the battles I’m just one of them but they are the hero, I’m just one among the heroes but I’m not the hero they are the heroes.

“ In this kind of work, one person cannot survive, it has to be group effort. And that is what we are doing- team effort.”

Describing the spirituality in business by different perspectives, it is simply embodying the personal values of honesty, integrity, efficiency, and good quality work, treating co-workers and employees as a human being in a responsible, caring way.

The “triple-bottom line”

It is no secret that employee turnover in the foodservice industry is one of the highest in the labor force. But while many quick-serve operators view high turnover as an inevitable part of business, dedication is the ultimate goal in keeping turnover low. Restaurant operators who show dedication to their employees through benefits programs will find that those employees show dedication back.

Are spirituality and profitability mutually exclusive? Bringing ethics and spiritual values into the workplace can lead to increased productivity and profitability as well as employee retention, customer loyalty, and brand reputation, according to a growing body of research. More employers are encouraging spirituality as a way to boost loyalty and enhance morale.

It is empathy for others particularly for the employees. There is so much pressure in the workplace, some of which may be physically-related due to being overworked. It becomes the responsibility of the entrepreneur to provide what could alleviate the conditions of the workers which can be done in different ways. One way is getting them out of their usual daily routine as a respite from work.

“It is undeniably happening that there will come a point when people get tired of working, it is also true for me. With this, having a break will do good for them. What I usually do is to enjoin everyone for a break during holy week for example and we go to swimming, bonding and the like and I provide a budget for that. This is how I reward them for working at times for 24/7 duty, with no holidays.”

Spirituality at work addresses human activities relating to personal development, compassion, meaningfulness and joy at work, honesty, trust, job commitment, and wellbeing of employees (Petchsawange & Duchan, 2012). To better understand worker's well-being, it is important to know about aspects of their lives besides work, such as social and domestic life.

“... But recently I also decided after many years to give holiday so that we can all have a rest. Although for them, they opted to have work than not to have as pay for a day of rest. In relation to that, I also allot budget for medicines in case someone will get sick.”

The workplace is a significant part of an individual’s life that affects his or her life and the wellbeing of the community (Harter, Schmidt & Keyes, 2002). Spirituality means that improving the life of one person is a multiplier that can improve others’ life until it reaches a community of persons.

“... The ones we hired are our former helpers at home. They are couple and we believe of their abilities, therefore we upgraded them into being a cook. Since they are helpers at home, they do not really have formal education. My agreement with them is that as long as they are staying with them as a worker, they will continue to extend help. In fact, one of them has his siblings also employed with us. I gave them chances to be employed despite of them not being educated.”

Love and spirituality are very much connected with motivation and change. People in the restaurant business struggle to think how to 'motivate' their people - as if motivation is some sort of force one applies to somebody. In fact everything that truly motivates people - whether to perform better, to be more dependable and committed, to take initiative, to be courageous, to do the right thing, to adapt to change, etc., can be included within love and spirituality. Love makes people believe in themselves and feel valued, and liberates them to have this same effect on others. This builds confidence and trust. Spirituality enables people to connect with each other and with the things that truly matter in the world and their lives. This gives people meaning and purpose and relevance, which is at the heart of true motivation.

Spirituality and Customer Service

Spirituality and customer service embrace the values of responsibility, integrity, moral, honesty, accountability, quality, cooperation, caring, service, intuition, loyalty, trustworthiness, respect, justice, guidance, motivation and passing benefits to concern. When they are doing customer service well, they are at their highest and best. They are serving each other, they are treating each other as if they have permanent and eternal value. They are in harmony with the deep truth of life, that all of us are astonishing beings who have mostly forgotten who they are. Maybe a deep connection, a spiritual commitment to being kind and helpful and of service to customers help them remember. For that moment, they can almost recall who they are and what they are supposed to be about. they can connect with the infinite best when they sacrifice their selfishness to other people and help them recall their own value.

"The nature of our business is labor intensive and that means they have to interact with our customers who are mostly students or faculty members. So now, we put emphasis on people having good values and with good religious upbringing. We are choosy in selecting people who will work for us. I have seen that over the years. It is difficult to get along with people if they do not have a good upbringing. Being good is something lasting."

". . .to make our customers to have a good experience in eating with us kaya para samin we do everything just to make one person, make one customer happy in a particular day that is already fulfillment on our part.

"I also discourage my workers into being irritable. No matter how small or big the item bought by a customer, they still have to express thanksgiving. I pointed out to them that our customers are number one. It is our ultimate goal to make a customers happy and fulfilled.

Spirituality in the restaurant business starts with the staff, the employees, having the right values because you cannot give anything that you do not possess. Valuing the customer means treating them always as number one, giving the best service, providing them the good experience that will allow them to patronize the business. The customer should be treated alike regardless of his purchase, from the simple candy to the most expensive food.

Spirituality towards the customer means having a good disposition, serving with a smile, a good greeting and a goodbye thank you. Making one customer happy during the encounter is a fulfillment on the part of the business owner and the staff during the service encounter. It is important to always serve the customer with a smile. Customer satisfaction is viral, it is a come on for the others and it can be a word of mouth advertising.

Spirituality in Leadership

Spiritual leadership involves the application of spiritual values and principles to the workplace. The spiritual leader understands the importance of employees finding meaning in their work and demonstrates a genuine concern for the "whole" person, not just the employee but even toward the customers. Understanding the need of the employees to exercise their faith and not depriving them of their religious needs is a kind of leadership.

"... I have been telling them to attend church first in the morning if it's Sunday or those who are supposed to go home early can go to church then. Anyways, there are nearby churches along Ermita. Many believed that being involved in spiritual activities like studying and prayer , meditation as such are most likely guided in their work."

Spirituality in the restaurant business can exist without proselytizing or pressuring individuals. In the case of effective leadership, we shall find that spirituality expresses itself not so much in words or preaching, but in the embodiment of spiritual values such as integrity, and in the demonstration of spiritual behavior such as expressing caring and concern. Giacalone & Jurkiewicz (2004) define workplace spirituality as framework of organizational values evidenced in the culture that promotes employees' experience of transcendence through the work process, facilitating their sense of being connected in a way that provides feelings of compassion and joy (p. 13). Many leadership theories emphasize the need for the leader to articulate an inspiring vision, but what is important is not so much words but rather actions: the level of ethics demonstrated, the respect and compassion shown to others.

Leadership is being able to show the employees that you are the master who know the craft of their business, that you can direct the business, lead and can even be left alone to get everything going. On top of this is treating everyone fairly, sharing the same food that you eat, and giving a portion of the gain of the business to show them that you value their contribution.

" As a restaurant owner, you must have certain traits or habits. I am the first person to come and the last person to go everyday regardless whether there are occasions or not. Even if I am sick I have to be there. I do not also mind doing stuff like what my workers do specially when someone is absent, I can patch in for them. I cannot stay back and simply watch them. It matters also that I know the work they do."

When leaders recognize employee contributions, employees feel better about the organization, they feel more of a sense of community, and they are more likely to stay with the organization and continue to contribute. Leadership research shows that recognition has a powerful effect on motivation and performance. A leader's use of motivating language, including clear explanations of tasks, rewards, and cultural values, as well as expressions of compassion or praise, has been demonstrated to increase worker job satisfaction and performance (Mayfield & Mayfield, 2002). Listening to others means not only acknowledging their concerns, but also recognizing and respecting good ideas. Truly listening to others and responding to their needs is another way to express caring and concern that is universally endorsed by spiritual paths.

"Your integrity in front of your employees has something to do with your being able to show first to them that you are capable of doing the work your all assigning to them. Show the right examples to them as to how to serve rightfully the customers. Be a role model to them."

Employees at all levels in the corporate world increasingly want to nourish their spirit and creativity. When they are encouraged to express their creativity, the result is a more fulfilled and sustainable the personal satisfaction of the staff. Spirituality was cited as the second most important factor in personal happiness.

Demonstrating concern for subordinates is particularly important for lower-level managers who work more closely with employees. The priority for most employees is that their leaders demonstrate caring and concern. Communication or interpersonal relationship skills as the most important quality of a good supervisor which can be done effectively by the restaurant owner since the organization is only small.

Spirituality is Values Contribution to the Community

Micro businesses like the restaurants owned by micro entrepreneurs form a dynamic, integral part of the market economy, providing goods and services and a gateway by which millions enter the

economic and social mainstream of the Philippine local and national economy. These micro-restaurant entrepreneurs provide goods that are lower in price than other competitors categorized as big businesses making their goods affordable to the ordinary masses.

"We do not necessarily earn much, enough earnings is good so you are capable of helping your employees."

More than providing excellent service for customers, the spiritual dimension indicates a larger sense of responsibility to contribute to the betterment of the world. Today's spiritual organization is deliberate in implementing a vision that is built around contributions to the betterment of mankind. The entrepreneurs do this in terms of providing good education to their children and even to the children of their employees.

"My vision for my family and also for the family of my helpers is to give them a chance to finish their studies. It is for them, for their future. I am so happy because for almost 9 years, one finished college, and one is done in high school and also one extended family member from my husband side graduated too."

"...the fact that I was able to help a nephew to finish college is already a joy on my end, because of this business, I was able to help a lot of relatives, almost 7 of them are done in college. I still need to help 4 more next year."

Micro-restaurant businesses are job creators, and most of those jobs are local jobs. Rather than having to commute to another city, employees work closer to home. Not only does this reduce traffic congestion, supporting local businesses also supports your fellow community members who work at them. The entrepreneurs in this study made it a different way. Since they are in Metro Manila, the employment they provided are for those in the provinces; workers who lack the opportunity for labour in their own localities. The opportunity for education has also been extended to poor family members.

"The ones whom we hired are our helpers at home. We have a couple whom we assigned separately in different branches and now we are sending them to school. I keep on telling them to also help their family members as well."

"...I have helped much of my relatives by sending them to school, the same example is being done by them once they finished studies- they also help their relatives. I support them in paying tuition fees. They come to us for help."

An entrepreneur's demonstration of caring and concern can go beyond the walls of the organization to make a commitment to the community as well. Spirituality promotes work outside of the organization that contributes to and "gives back" to society through community and volunteer service. None of the entrepreneurs in this study do volunteer works but they give back to the community something that alleviates suffering souls in simple way, giving food to the hungry.

"When someone is begging, do not give them money, give them food instead feed them, let them sit there. When you really wanted to help, give them food to eat, you can also offer a job, or you can help them work abroad."

While the small restaurant business may not exactly provide the kind of products and services that multi-national corporations may provide, entrepreneurs for that matter, basically understand that part of their role is to make the world a better place through the products or services that they sell catering to all levels of customers, providing employment to both skilled and non-skilled workers and providing a chance for a good life to their immediate families by providing the help in the form of education.

Spirituality in the Face of Challenges

Restauranting is more of a calling rather than a job. And even those who think they are called to it, are

often times completely unprepared for the amount of work and stress that comes with being a restaurant owner. One of the greatest challenges that the entrepreneurs experienced was stress. They worry about everything that goes in the restaurant from the opening and closing time, the menu to be prepared, sourcing of ingredients and their staff – from arguments to finding cooks. Worry and stress come hand in hand because when the restaurant is busy, the entrepreneur worries about the service of the staff, when the business is low, they worry about the money.

As the owners of the restaurant, they put in very long days and evenings to be sure everything is going on smoothly. There are no holidays and weekends become so busy also especially for one who even does catering. Being at home is not a rest because they continuously plan for the next day.

“Despite of being tired, I Still need to be awake as early as 1:30 am and at 2:00am, I am already in the market and I have been doing this for almost 30 years. What keeps me going is my spirituality. I do not think my body alone cannot do it, it is always mind over body. You have to be responsible- to your children and to your employees.”

“I am the person who first to come in and the last to go home regardless of whatever occasion there is. Even if I’m sick, I still have to report because I wanted to set a good example for my people. There are times when a boss is late, what will happen in the opening, specially our business is food, therefore we have to be prompt, that’s why I am the first and the last to go.”

Another challenge is theft done by the workers. You may not realize that slowly the business is being drained and the possibility that other workers will do the same. Since the offense may be considered petty, the police authorities were out of the picture. The problem is usually confronted by the owner directly, even to the extent of giving another chance or simply having a forgiving heart but it does not stop there. When something wrong is done, it should be curtailed, sometimes to the extent of firing the person rather than damage the whole business and affect the other employees. Spirituality in business also means fairness and justice.

“There were also cases of me hiring people who are not worthy of trust. They have stolen money from us. That is why it is also advisable to do inventory so you will know what is needed to be replenished for the next day. I am surprised when our stocks are easily lost, then I found out they are stealing stocks like whole chicken. It is considered a threat in business. They throw in the trash but it is wrapped carefully then afterwards, they get it and sell it.”

Another challenge in the restaurant business is competition. To stay competitive in the market, privately-owned restaurants must offer something unique to set themselves apart from the big-box restaurants. The big challenge is to continuously produce innovative menus within the affordability of the consumers.

Then what sustains the micro-restaurant entrepreneurs in their business? For them it is spirituality – the rope that makes them clinging that everything will turn out right. It is the belief and the practice that every time they wake up is a prayer of thanksgiving and a prayer of guidance, a prayer of physical, emotional and spiritual strength to hurdle the day-to-day activities. Spirituality is asking guidance to deal with difficult customers, to show values to the employees that such may serve also as their guide being the frontlines in the business. Spirituality is imploring the continuous success of the business so that they can continue with their intention to improve the life of other people by providing education.

When so much stress gets in the way . . .

“... When I got so stressed, I just step back, meditate and pray. After that I will feel a little comfort- I can make better decisions afterwards.”

“I also told my workers to attend church on Sundays, they can do it before or after going to work. If they can see that you value spirituality, it sends also a message to them to fear God.”

Indeed, owning and managing a restaurant is a big challenge.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Spirituality is a connection to God regardless of religious affiliation, it is the constant communication through prayers, to be guided in their everyday business and possessing good values toward the food they serve, the customers they interact with and the employees who work for them. Under the context of spirituality the proponents' vision is to help and uplift the stakeholders for they do not only benefit from earning but also their employees by giving the basic needs and providing education as means of having a better future when they leave the company. Spirituality is framed into vision, giving better future for the family and its employees and the character as well as integrity.
2. Under the context of spirituality, the entrepreneurs were able to overcome the threats and challenges because of its values it carries and it projects to its employees. Focusing on good customer's services, quality of product being served, transparent to customers with regard to the current situation with regard to prices if there is a need for increase and earning trust from that resulted to customer loyalty.
3. In sustaining the motivation of the entrepreneurs, it is concluded that spirituality gives an entrepreneur an extra energy, as described by one of the respondents. Part of the spiritual context is prayer; it should be done before after the restaurant operation.
4. They are not running of strength for they believe that when they pray and dedicate everything they do to God, God will strengthen their soul and rejuvenate their weary body.

RECOMMENDATION

1. The vision of the entrepreneurs is for the betterment of its family and employees whom mostly are their relatives. But the idea is limited to micro-scale. The vision of the entrepreneurs should also include growth of the business. The bigger the business becomes the more it will be able to help and does not limit its assistance to its relatives, but also to other people. As such, it is recommended that entrepreneurs should further enhance their entrepreneurial skills in order for them to fulfill their goals and objectives, and provide continuous sustenance to their business and people. Likewise, the continuous practice of corporate social responsibility should be intensified in order to maintain integrity, honesty and good quality work.
2. The vision of the entrepreneur should be cascaded and shared to the employees in order to drive them to persevere, dream big and empower them to fully implement the vision and vision of the organization.
3. The spiritual context should be part of regular activities of the restaurants. Activities and programs such as annual retreats, recollections and team building should be integrated in the annual operation of business. Likewise, prayer before and after should be a regular activity of the restaurant owners.
4. It is also recommended that as an act of generosity of the entrepreneurs to give assistance to their employees such as cash advance, medical assistance and school expenses. Moreover, the inclusion of family member in some activities like Christmas party and outing can be considered. Such act would entice more the employees to do better in their job.
5. Proper mentoring on the new employees should be done in order train them and provide knowledge regarding the business
6. The newbies should attend seminars and training pertaining to the establishment of business
7. Further study can be made using other variables in order to replicate the research.

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